

Proposing conference leadership index to measure scholarly impact of academic institutions: An empirical study in artificial intelligence field

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Abstract

Traditionally the evaluation of scholarly impact of academic institutions is mainly based on publication and citation data. This study has considered the gatekeeper role of committee member of prestigious academic conferences in a systematic way, especially for research areas where conference plays an essential role in scholarly communication. A novel indicator, the conference leadership index (CLI), is proposed. The indicator has considered key influential factors including the authority of the conference, the level of the position, the scale of the committee and the diversity of involved conferences. Artificial intelligence field is taken for empirical study to illustrate the process of calculating the indicator. Results show that conference leadership index is able to reflect the scholarly impact of academic institutions, but in a different way compared with traditional bibliometric indicators and is complementary to patent performance. Top academic institutions in AI filed were identified, among which giant enterprises are dominating. USA has absolute advantage in leading the AI conferences, although China is thriving and may have surpassed USA to be the largest source country of Web of Science papers. These results indicate that conference leadership index is a useful novel indicator and could be applied to many other research fields.

Introduction

Evaluation of academic institutions is widely concerned by scholars and policymakers. Many science policy decision-makings, including funding allocation and project approval, are based mainly on the evaluation result (García, Rodríguez-Sánchez, Fdez-Valdivia, Robinson-García, & Torres-Salinas, 2013; Barnes, 2014). The evaluation would also help identify core institutions in different research areas. This is useful for tracking research fronts, following cutting-edge technology, informing talent evaluation, establishing benchmarking institutions, and furthermore, providing reference for making the efficient university-industry-research policy (Aranguren, Canto-Farachala, & Wilson, 2021).

For the evaluation of academic institutions, scholarly impact is an essential and perhaps the most important dimension. The evaluation framework consists of different categories of indicators, including knowledge transition, recognition, bibliometrics, research funding and so on (Pulford, Price, Quach, & Bates, 2020). Scholar impact refers to the impact that the academic institution has produced on various types of scholarly activities, including the impact on scholarly thoughts, professional theories and applied practices (Aguinis, Suárez-González, Lannelongue, & Joo, 2012). The evaluation is mainly conducted based on both peer review and quantitative measurement. Peer review is powerful and widely adopted. However, it is expensive and time consuming, and highly relies on expert's experience which could be subjective and potentially biased. Quantitative measurement is often used as supplementary and occasionally used as the primary way of evaluation (Csomós, 2020).

Traditionally the quantitative evaluation of academic institutions is mainly based on publication and patent data (Hermanu, Sondari, Dimiyati, & Sari, 2022; Vanclay, & Bornmann, 2012). Most commonly used indicators are number of publications, number of citations, average number of citations, number of patents and other composite indicators, for example, h index and mean normalized citation score (Hammarfelt, Nelhans, Eklund, & Åström, 2016). In addition to these indicators that focus on outputs of academic institutions, other indicators that focus on scholars are also proposed. For example, scholar's editorship in journals is explored as an important

measure of the impact. Wu, Li, Lu and Li (2018) proposed the journal editorship index (JEI) to evaluate the impact of academic institutions in the economic field.

Scholar's role in academic conference is considered to have reflected the received recognition by academic institution (Bucur, Kifor, & Mărginean, 2018). In many research areas like computer science, conferences are the major channels for scholarly communication, and are playing a more vital role than journals. These conferences are shaping future research direction, guiding allocation of scholarly resources, and breeding innovative thinking. For research areas where conferences are primary communication channel, conference leadership would be a useful data source for measuring the scholarly impact. It is not only a reflection of social capital like reputation, but also a sign of soft power in scholarly resources.

In the comprehensive evaluation framework, editorship in conference proceedings is included as an important indicator (Bacon, Paul, Stewart, & Mukhopadhyay, 2012). Invitation to speak at conferences is also proposed to measure individual scholar's outcome (Cole, Boyd, Aslanyan, & Bates, 2014). However, to our best knowledge, contribution as committee member of academic conference has not been explored. Leading a conference, especially a conference with high reputation, is a strong signal of scholarly impact. It is similar to the gatekeeper role of a journal, except that conference is more dynamic than journal. Take artificial intelligence as example, China is leading in the world rankings based on paper data (Yu, Xu, & Fujita, 2019; Ho, & Wang, 2020) or patent data (Gao, & Ding, 2022; Rikap, & Lundvall, 2021), but the performance as reflected by conference leadership remains untapped.

Therefore, the key research question of this study is, how can scholarly impact of academic institutions be measured from the perspective of conference leadership? Different factors would be taken into consideration to construct the conference leadership index. The proposed index will be calculated for artificial intelligence field, and further compared with some traditional indicators to demonstrate its usefulness.

Process of constructing the Conference Leadership Index (CLI)

Artificial intelligence field is taken for empirical study, because it is leading the next generation information technology and conference is its dominant channel for communicating the latest research. In the following part, we would demonstrate the process of constructing conference leader index for artificial intelligence field.

Data collection

There is a huge number of academic conferences. It is considered that only taking leading position in academic conferences of high quality and good reputation would contribute to the scholarly impact of scholars and academic institutions.

Research.com is a widely used platform in computer science area, and since 2014 has provided reliable data for related scientific contribution, enabling the researchers to stay informed of the latest conferences and publications. Nowadays, the platform covers 25 broad category subjects under which there are more small category subjects. Artificial intelligence is one of 14 small categories in *Computer Science* subject. In the category of artificial intelligence, 281 conferences were listed and ranked. The platform has calculated a comprehensive Impact Score for each conference to measure the scholarly impact. The impact score takes into consideration the h index of the conference, number of involved top scientists and number of years¹. The score is deemed to be authoritative and creditable in computer science. Therefore, from the

¹ <https://research.com/our-methodology>

ranking of academic conferences in artificial intelligence in 2021 on Research.com, conferences with impact score over 5 were selected as sample for research. In total, 32 high quality academic conferences were selected, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Top conferences in artificial intelligence field (Impact score > 5)

NO.	Conference	Impact Score	NO.	Conference	Impact Score
1	CVPR	51.98	17	SIGIR	8.74
2	NIPS	33.49	18	ICDE	8.25
3	ICCV	32.51	19	ICIP	7.59
4	ECCV	25.91	20	ICDM	7.59
5	AAAI	25.57	21	ICAFG	7.59
6	ICML	18.48	22	ISIT	7.26
7	SIGKDD	13.53	23	IJCNN	7.09
8	IJCAI	11.71	24	INTERSPEECH	6.6
9	ICLR	11.38	25	BMVC	5.94
10	ACL	10.56	26	ACCV	5.61
11	WSDM	10.56	27	EACL	5.61
12	IROS	10.06	28	SDM	5.45
13	SIGMOD	10.06	29	ITSC	5.45
14	AISTATS	9.9	30	IV	5.45
15	CIKM	9.4	31	LAK	5.28
16	EMNLP	9.24	32	RECSYS	5.12

For the selected conferences, the list of committee members for each conference from year 2012 to year 2021 were collected from data sources such as the official conference website, the conference brochure and conference recordings. The collected data include the committee member's title, name and affiliated institutions. It is found that most top AI conferences were held annually, for example, the CVPR and NIPS. A few of them were held biannually, for example, ICCV and ECCV. Some conferences were held without a fixed period, for example, IJCAI.

In total, the 32 top AI conferences were held 293 times in the 10 years. Because several times of conferences cannot be retrieved, eventually data for 280 times (95% of total number) of conferences were harvested, and in total there were 7444 records. The committee member's title and affiliated institutions were further normalized. As regards the title, different titles of the same meaning were merged, for example, chairs are merged with chair, industry chair is merged with industrial chair, finance chair is merged with financial chair. As regards the affiliated institutions, the full name is merged with the abbreviation. In case one committee member is affiliated with several different institutions, fractional counting method is adopted when attributing the scholar to different institutions.

Weighting strategy of different influencing factors

After data collection and data cleaning, different influencing factors of conference leadership index were weighted, including the scholarly impact of the conference, the level of the position and the scale of the committee.

(1) The scholarly impact of the conference. Conference weight (CW) has considered the overall scholarly impact of the academic conference. Higher scholarly impact of the conference would bring higher weight. The impact score calculated by Research.com was used to weight the conference. The score has comprehensively considered the quality and quantity of both scholars

and papers of the conference in the previous three years. Therefore, the score could properly measure the scholarly impact of the conference.

(2) The level of the position. Level weight (LW) has considered the importance of different positions in the committee and is determined by both the scholarly relevance and the scholarly contribution. Conference committee positions were classified as two categories, the scholarly position and the non-scholarly position. Combined with the importance of their scholarly contribution, these positions were classified into 4 levels from 3 to 0, as shown in Table 2. Different levels are then weighted according to the number of members in each level. The more important the position is, the lower the number of committee members is, and consequently the higher the weight value is. In the research sample, the number of level 3 committee members is 1264, the number of level 2 committee members is 1692, the number of level 1 committee members is 2325. The ratio is about 2:3:4. Suppose that weight value for level 1 committee member is 1, then weight value for level 3 committee member is 4:2 which equals to 2, and weight value of level 2 committee member is 4:3 which is approximately 1.3.

Table 2. Classification and weight of different committee members

Level	Title of the position	Num.	Weight
3	Program Chair, General Chair, General Vice Chair	1264	2
2	Honorary Chair, Panel Chair, Workshop Chair, Awards Committee, Award Chair, Tutorial Chair, Cup Chair, Application Program Chairs, Short Paper Chairs, Best Paper Track Co-Chairs	1692	1.3
1	Industry Engagement Chair/Co-Chair, Industry Chair, Practitioner Track Chairs, Industrial Program Chair, Technical Program Chair, Hackathon Organizers, Video Chair, Integrated AI Capabilities Track Cochairs, Late Breaking Results Co-Chairs, Applied Data Science Invited Talk Chair, Virtual Infrastructure Chairs, AI History Panel Chair, Case Study and Industry Track Chairs, Case Studies Chairs, Senior Advisor, Advisory Committee Chair, SRW Faculty Advisors, Local Arrangement Chair, Local Chair, Local Organization Chair, Area Program Co-Chairs, Area General Co-Chairs, Asia Pacific Track Co-Chairs, Workflow Chair, Demo Chair, Keynote Speakers, Exhibition and Demo Chair, Inclusion & Accessibility Co-Chair, Doctoral Consortium Chair, Innovation Program Chair, Sustainability Chair, Reproducibility Chair, Analytic up Chair, Evaluation Chairs, Findings Chairs, Conference Logistics, Special Event Chair, Challenge Co-Chairs, Survey Track Chairs, Student Scholarship co-Chairs, Student Research Competition Chairs, Organizing Committee Chair, Proceedings Chair	2325	1
0	Finance Chair, Publication Chair, Poster Chair, Conference Secretariat, Secretary, International Program Chair, Communication Chair, Press Chairs, Social Event Chair, Meetup Chairs, Socio-cultural Inclusion Chairs, Social Media Chair, Media and Publicity Chair, Publicity Chair, Website Chair, Childcare Policy & Grant Coordinator, Sponsorship Chair, Student Volunteer Chair, Registration Chair	2134	0

The scale of the committee. Scale weight (SW) has considered the influence of scale on the scholarly impact. Following the way of processing editorship data proposed by Frey and Rost (2010), scale of conference committee is classified into three sections based on the ranking of number of committee members. Suppose weight of conferences of which the scale ranks 33.3%~66.6% is 1, then weight of conferences ranking within the top 33.3% is 1.2, and the weight of conferences ranking below the bottom 66.6% is 0.8.

Calculation of the conference leadership index

In the first step, individual researcher's scholarly impact is calculated by constructing the conference impact index (CII) of which the formula is shown in formula (1).

$$CII_i = \sum_{j=1}^n CW_{ij} \times LW_{ij} \times SW_{ij} \quad (1)$$

In the above formula, CW_{ij} represents conference weight of conference j where researcher i participates, LW_{ij} represents level weight of the position that researcher i takes at conference j , SW_{ij} represents scale weight of conference j where researcher i participates, n represents the total number of academic conferences that researcher i takes position in.

In the second step, conference leadership index of academic institutions is calculated by integrating individual researcher's CII and considering the diversity factor. Each researcher's CII score is attributed to the affiliated institutions using fractional counting method. Diversity factor (DF) refers to that when two academic institutions have achieved the same score accumulated from individual researchers, the academic institution that take position in higher number of different conferences is considered to have higher scholarly impact, because it reaches more diverse academic group. For example, both institution A and institution B have score value of 100, institution A has 100 researchers to take position in one conference while institution B has 100 researchers taking position in ten different conferences, then institution B has achieved broader scholarly impact. Suppose institution m has researchers taking position in x conference committees, then the diversity factor DF_m is calculated as follows.

$$DF_m = 1 + \ln(x) \quad (2)$$

With formula (2), on one hand the diversity factor is taken into consideration, on the other hand extreme situation is avoided. After integrating the diversity factor, conference leadership index is calculated as in formula (3).

$$CLI_m = DF_m * \sum_{i=1}^j CII_{im} \quad (3)$$

In the above formula (3), CLI_m represents the scholarly impact of academic institution m , DF_m represents the diversity factor of institution m that involve positions in different conferences, CII_{im} represents the conference impact index of researcher i from institution m , and j represents the total number of researchers who take position in conference committee from institution m .

Empirical analysis

Descriptive statistics of committee member data in AI conferences

Statistical result shows that in total 4,431 researchers from 1,483 academic institutions have taken position in committees of high-quality AI conferences in the 10 years period. Among the researchers in conference committee, 69% of them appear once, 3% of them appear more than 5 times. The top 10 researchers as regards frequency of being committee member is listed in Table 3. As shown in Table 3, professor Jie Tang from Tsinghua university ranks the first position, followed by professor Brendan Morris and professor Wei Wang. These researchers are highly active organizers in top AI conferences.

Table 3. Active researchers in top AI conferences based on frequency of being committee members (Top 10)

Name	Frequency	Affiliated institution	Country
Jie Tang	17	Tsinghua University	China
Brendan Morris	14	University of Nevada, Las Vegas	USA
Wei Wang	14	University of California, Los Angeles	USA
Zhi-Hua Zhou	13	Nanjing University	China
Jian Pei	13	Simon Fraser University	Canada
Hui Xiong	13	University of Delaware, Baidu etc.	USA
Xindong Wu	13	Mininglamp Academy of Sciences etc.	China
Toshio Fukuda	13	Meijo University, Nagoya University	Japan
Jingrui He	13	Stevens Institute of Technology, IBM etc.	USA
Yan Liu	12	University of Southern California	USA

The ranking of academic institutions based on frequency of being committee members is shown in Table 4. The top 3 institutions are all enterprises including Microsoft, Google and IBM. Tsinghua university (ranking the fourth) and Chinese academy of science (ranking the sixth) from China are in the front position.

Table 4. Active institutions in top AI conferences based on frequency of committee membership (Top 10)

Institution	Frequency	Ranking
Microsoft	190	1
Google	166	2
IBM	100	3
Tsinghua University	97	4
Carnegie Mellon University	79	5
Chinese Academy of Sciences	79	6
University of Southern California	70	7
Amazon	70	8
University of Edinburgh	57	9
Arizona State University	56	10

Result of individual researcher's conference impact index

According to formula (1), for each researcher in the sample the conference impact index is calculated. Consequently, the high-impact scholars in AI field are recognized. Table 5 has listed the top 10 researchers. As shown in Table 5, high frequency of being committee members may not necessarily indicate high conference impact index. For example, Jingrui He has been a committee member for 13 times, however, most of her positions are not the critical ones in high-impact conferences. In comparison, although David Forsyth has only 4 records of being committee member, his conference impact index ranks the first position. He has been the general chair and program chair of CVPR, and he has also been the general chair for ICCV. Among the top 10 researchers, professor Tinne Tuytelaars has the least frequency of being committee member, but has taken important positions as general chair and program chair of CVPR and program chair of ECCV. Professor Zhihua Zhou from Nanjing university has the

highest frequency of being committee members and has taken important positions in AAAI, SIGKDD, ICDM and so on.

Table 5. Researchers based on conference impact index (Top 10)

Ranking	Researcher	Affiliated institution	Frequency of being committee member	Conference impact index
1	David Forsyth	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	4	363.9
2	Hugo Larochelle	Google	8	307.3
3	Kristen Grauman	University of Texas at Austin	4	305.5
4	Tamara Berg	University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill	4	275.5
5	Zhi-Hua Zhou	Nanjing University	13	273.6
6	Peter Stone	University of Texas at Austin	7	269.5
7	Rama Chellappa	Maryland University	7	261.1
8	Jingyi Yu	Shanghai University of Science and Technology	5	257.4
9	Tinne Tuytelaars	Catholic University of Louvain	3	249.4
10	Sven Koenig	University of Southern California	8	248.9

Result of academic institution's conference leadership index

According to formula (3), for each academic institution the conference leadership index is calculated, as shown in Table 6. There are 284 academic institutions with CLI score being 0, indicating that researchers from these institutions are acting non-scholarly role in the conference committee. This is because: (1) As shown in Table 2, 2,134 out of 7,415 committee members are classified as non-scholarly positions of which the weight is 0. (2) Only 32 high quality academic conferences in AI field are selected. It does not necessarily mean that the 284 academic institutions have no scholarly contribution to the AI field.

Table 6. Distribution of institutions based on range of CLI score

Range of CLI score	Number of institutions
0	284
(0,1000]	1138
(1000,2000]	35
(2000,3000]	14
(3000,4000]	7
Over 4000	5

Table 7 has listed the top 20 institutions based on the conference leadership index. Above all Microsoft and Google are ranking the first and second position, and are far ahead of the third institution Carnegie Mellon university. Among the top 10 institutions, USA enterprises dominate with Microsoft, Google, IBM, Facebook and Amazon, while the other five institutions are well-known universities mainly from USA as well, except Tsinghua university from China. This suggests that giant high-tech industrial enterprises are playing leading role in top AI conferences, and USA institutions are holding firmly the leading position in AI conferences.

Table 7. Top academic institutions based on conference leadership index (Top 20)

Ranking	Institution	Affiliated country	CLI
1	Microsoft	US	13384.5
2	Google	US	10834.1
3	Carnegie	US	6538.1
4	Facebook	US	4650.3
5	University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign	US	4640.6
6	IBM	US	3675.3
7	University of Southern California	US	3452.3
8	Amazon	US	3445.8
9	MIT	US	3445.3
10	Tsinghua University	China	3107.6
11	Washington University	US	3051.2
12	Stanford University	US	3047.0
13	University of California, San Diego	US	2697.1
14	University of Pennsylvania	US	2619.8
15	Chinese Academy of Science	China	2499.1
16	University of Michigan	US	2435.8
17	Edinburgh University	UK	2414.8
18	Institut national de recherche en informatique et en automatique	FRANCE	2398.7
19	Johns Hopkins University	US	2398.1
20	Oxford University	UK	2382.1

The country distribution of top 100 institutions based on conference leadership index is shown in Figure 1. In total 18 countries were involved. Among the top 100 institutions, 47 institutions are from USA, 14 institutions are from China, 8 institutions are from UK, 6 institutions are from Australia. The other countries would have only no more than 3 institutions in the ranking. This indicates that USA has absolute advantage in leading the top AI conferences. China is also thriving but has large gap compared with USA. As regards type of the institutions, most of them (94 institutions) are renowned universities, a few (13 institutions) of them are large enterprises. In contrast with universities, enterprises are the minority but have very high impact, for example, the top 3 institutions are enterprises. Moreover, there are 4 other type of institutions.

Fig. 1. Number of institutions by country based on conference leadership index (Top 100)

Discussion

Comparison with ranking result based on publication data

To reveal the characteristics of conference leadership index, we have selected the Ace Rankings (<https://www.acemap.info/ranking>) in artificial intelligence filed in 2021 for comparison's purpose. The ranking is developed based on the citation data of articles published in level A conferences and journals recommended by CCF (China Computer Federation), and has ranked the related academic institutions and prestigious researchers.

Kendall correlation analysis was conducted between ranking based on conference leadership index and ranking based on h index, as well as ranking based on total number of citations. Correlation result shows that CLI-based ranking is significantly correlated with ranking based on h index, the coefficient is 0.357. CLI-based ranking is also significantly correlated with that based on total number of citations, the coefficient is 0.303.

The above results indicate that conference leadership index could measure the scholarly impact of academic institutions from a different dimension as reflected by publication data. On one hand, top academic institutions as measured by conference leadership index are highly overlapped with top institutions as measured by h index or total number of citations, indicating that prestigious institutions under traditional evaluation are also performing well in the proposed measure. On the other hand, several institutions have achieved quite different rankings as exemplified in Table 8. For example, Xi'an Jiaotong University ranks relatively to the front position by h index and total number of citations, but from perspective of conference leadership index it ranks much lower. Similar situation occurs for NVIDIA, École Normale Supérieure and Adobe systems. The underlying reason could be either these institutions have focused mainly on producing articles rather than organizing conferences, or they are not influential enough to take leading position in conferences.

Table 8. Example institutions with significantly different ranking position in CLI-based and publication-based rankings (<https://www.acemap.info/ranking>)

Institution	Ranking by h index	Ranking by total number of citations	Ranking by CLI
Xi'an Jiaotong University	47	11	328

Nvidia	48	49	960
École Normale Supérieure	38	40	1140
Adobe Systems	19	30	820

Comparison with ranking result based on patent data

In addition to publication data, patent data is often used for evaluating the impact of academic institutions. For comparison’s purpose, ranking of institutions based on number of patents is calculated. IncoPat is widely used patent database for conducting patent analysis (Han, Lin, Sun, Wang, & Yuan, 2022). Patent data from January 2012 to December 2021 were retrieved using keyword Artificial Intelligence to search in title and abstract. In total, 68,424 patents from 60 countries or regions were retrieved.

Kendall correlation analysis was conducted between ranking based on conference leadership index and ranking based on number of patents. Result shows that the correlation between two rankings is -0.007, indicating that conference leadership index is reflecting completely different type of impact with that of patents. Enterprises would usually pay more attention to patent application and the subsequent business value. Therefore, most enterprises have relatively good performance in the patent ranking. In comparison, research institutions put more efforts in publishing academic papers and participating academic conferences. Nevertheless, there are outstanding research institutions ranking high in both rankings, as shown in Table 9. For example, Microsoft ranks the first position using conference leadership index while ranks the 19th position using number of patents. IBM, Tsinghua university and China academy of science also have good performance in both rankings. These institutions are considered to have more comprehensive impact.

Table 9. Institutions that have good performance in both rankings based on conference leadership index and number of patents

Institution	Ranking based on conference leadership index	Ranking based on number of patents
Microsoft	1	19
IBM	6	11
Tsinghua university	10	27
China academy of science	15	29

Conclusion

Previous evaluation of scholarly impact for academic institutions are mainly based on publication and citation data. A few studies have included scholar’s performance in conference in the comprehensive evaluation framework, but contribution as committee member of academic conference remain untapped, especially not in a systematic way. This study contributes to a more comprehensive view of the scholarly impact by considering the conference leadership, because in many research areas conferences are playing the vital role in scholarly communication. In artificial intelligence area, China has surpassed USA as regards number of publications in Web of Science. It would be interesting to look at it from the perspective of conference leadership to have deeper understanding of the result. For empirical study, committee member data of top 32 AI conferences with Research.com impact score over 5 were collected. The dataset covers 280 times of conferences from year 2012 to year 2021 that involved 1483 academic institutions. Major conclusions of this study are as follows.

(1) A novel indicator, the conference leadership index (CLI), was proposed to measure the scholarly impact of academic institutions from perspective of conference leadership. The conference leadership index is a weighted indicator that has taken into consideration the authority of the conference, the level of held position, the scale of the committee as well as the diversity of involved conferences.

(2) The proposed conference leadership index would be able to reflect the scholarly impact of academic institutions but presents difference with that reflected by traditional publication and citation data. The CLI-based ranking is significantly correlated with both the ranking based on h index ($r=0.357$) and the ranking based on number of publications ($r=0.303$). Meanwhile, there are institutions that have quite different performance in the two types of rankings. This indicates that conference leadership and research productivity are related yet different dimensions of scholarly impact. Conference leadership brings more comprehensive scholarly impact. On one hand, holding the conference leadership role is a good symbol of academic reputation. On the other hand, being a conference chair helps determine the scope of accepted papers and many other aspects of the conference and therefore to some extent shape the direction of academic focus. In comparison, research productivity and citations reflect more the impact on peer researchers by measuring to what extent the other scholars have referenced one's work. While achieving good academic impact via high number of publications and citations contribute a lot (which probably explains why ranking based on conference leadership index and ranking based on h index or number of publications are significantly correlated), conference leaders are selected for several other reasons, such as individual charm, social capital, this can make the two rankings have difficult results.

(3) Top academic institutions in AI filed were identified according to conference leadership index. It is unexpected to see that enterprises are leading the AI conferences. Microsoft and Google are ranking the first and second position, and are far ahead of the third position, Carnegie Mellon university.

(4) USA has absolute advantage in leading the AI conferences, although China is thriving and ranking the second position. In the top 100 institutions, 47 institutions are from USA while only 13 institutions are from China. In the top 10 institutions, 9 institutions are from USA while only 1 institution is from China.

(5) The proposed conference leadership index is reflecting completely different type of impact with that of patent data, and they could be complementary to each other. The CLI-based ranking has very low correlation with the ranking based on number of patents, although some institutions would perform well in both rankings. For example, Tsinghua university and China academy of science from China, Microsoft and IBM from USA.

To conclude, the conference leadership index proposed in the study has complemented the traditional bibliometric analysis for evaluating scholarly impact of academic institutions, especially for those disciplines where conference play an essential role in scholarly communication. The conference leadership index has also provided a novel perspective to measure the impact of academic institutions as gatekeeper of science. Although artificial intelligence area is taken for empirical study, the conference leadership index is applicable to a wide variety of research areas. Moreover, the study has used impact score provided by Research.com to measure the impact of conference, according to previous studies, there are plenty of other indicators that could be used to measure the impact of conference. To better

customize the conference leadership index, one may simply substitute the impact score with some other indicator in the formula.

Following the recommendation of Leiden Manifesto (Hicks, Wouters, Waltman, De Rijcke, & Rafols, 2015), the CLI indicator is designed to measure the institutional level performance and provide only reference for peer review process. The indicator is with the flexibility that users could customize the formula according to their own evaluation target. The study is not without limitation. It has focused particularly the committee membership as indicator of conference leadership, while the other factors, such as number of ad hoc reviewing, and invitation to speak for the conference, are not considered. It must also be noticed that the proposed indicator does not normalize the impact of conferences that belong to different sub-fields. In fact, it is difficult to distinguish under artificial intelligence field the more refined research direction such as computer vision, machine learning and natural language processing.

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References

- Aguinis, H., Suárez-González, I., Lannelongue, G., & Joo, H. (2012). Scholarly impact revisited. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 26(2), 105-132.
- Aranguren, M. J., Canto-Farachala, P., & Wilson, J. R. (2021). Transformative academic institutions: An experimental framework for understanding regional impacts of research. *Research Evaluation*, 30(2), 191-200.
- Bacon, D. R., Paul, P., Stewart, K. A., & Mukhopadhyay, K. (2012). A new tool for identifying research standards and evaluating research performance. *Journal of marketing education*, 34(2), 194-208.
- Barnes, C. (2014). The emperor's new clothes: the h-index as a guide to resource allocation in higher education. *Journal of Higher Education Policy and Management*, 36(5), 456-470.
- Bucur, A., Kifor, C., & Mărginean, S. (2018). Evaluation of the Quality and Quantity of Research Results in Higher Education. *Quality and Quantity*, 52: 101-118.
- Cole DC, Boyd A, Aslanyan G, & Bates I. (2014). Indicators for Tracking Programmes to Strengthen Health Research Capacity in Lower- and Middle-Income Countries: a Qualitative Synthesis. *Health Research Policy and Systems*. 12: 17.
- Csomós, G. (2020). Introducing recalibrated academic performance indicators in the evaluation of individuals' research performance: A case study from Eastern Europe. *Journal of Informetrics*, 14(4), 101073.
- Frey, B. S., & Rost, K. (2010). Do rankings reflect research quality? *Journal of Applied Economics*, 13(1), 1-38.
- García, J. A., Rodríguez-Sánchez, R., Fdez-Valdivia, J., Robinson-García, N., & Torres-Salinas, D. (2013). Benchmarking research performance at the university level with information theoretic measures. *Scientometrics*, 95(1), 435-452.
- Gao, H., & Ding, X. (2022). The research landscape on the artificial intelligence: a bibliometric analysis of recent 20 years. *Multimedia Tools and Applications*, 81(9), 12973-13001.
- Hammarfelt, B., Nelhans, G., Eklund, P., & Åström, F. (2016). The heterogeneous landscape of bibliometric indicators: Evaluating models for allocating resources at Swedish universities. *Research Evaluation*, 25(3), 292-305.
- Han M., Lin H., Sun D., Wang J., & Yuan J. (2022). The Eco-Friendly Side of Analyst Coverage: The Case of Green Innovation. *IEEE Transactions on Engineering Management*, <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/9712651>.

- Hermanu, A. I., Sondari, M. C., Dimiyati, M., & Sari, D. (2022). Study on university research performance based on systems theory: systematic literature review. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, 35(4), 447-472.
- Hicks, D., Wouters, P., Waltman, L., De Rijcke, S., & Rafols, I. (2015). Bibliometrics: the Leiden Manifesto for research metrics. *Nature*, 520(7548), 429-431.
- Ho, Y. S., & Wang, M. H. (2020). A bibliometric analysis of artificial intelligence publications from 1991 to 2018. *COLLNET Journal of Scientometrics and Information Management*, 14(2), 369-392.
- Pulford, J. , Price, N. , Quach, J. A. , & Bates, I. . (2020). Measuring the outcome and impact of research capacity strengthening initiatives: a review of indicators used or described in the published and grey literature. *F1000 Research*, 9, 517.
- Rikap, C., & Lundvall, B. Å. (2021). China's Catching-Up Process and Its Emergence as a Potential Lead Country in Artificial Intelligence. In *The Digital Innovation Race* (pp. 121-144). Palgrave Macmillan, Cham.
- Vanclay, J. K., & Bornmann, L. (2012). Metrics to evaluate research performance in academic institutions: A critique of ERA 2010 as applied in forestry and the indirect H2 index as a possible alternative. *Scientometrics*, 91(3), 751-771.
- Wu, D., Li, J., Lu, X., & Li, J. (2018). Journal editorship index for assessing the scholarly impact of academic institutions: An empirical analysis in the field of economics. *Journal of Informetrics*, 12(2), 448-460.
- Yu, D., Xu, Z., & Fujita, H. (2019). Bibliometric analysis on the evolution of applied intelligence. *Applied Intelligence*, 49(2), 449-462.